

SMALL AIRWAYS AND THEIR LESIONS IN COPD (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. *This article reviews key aspects of the study of the small airways and their role in the pathogenesis of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Modern diagnostic and treatment methods aimed at early detection and therapeutic effects on the small airways are described. Particular attention is paid to new technologies of inhalation therapy, which provide more accurate delivery of drugs to the peripheral parts of the lungs, which helps reduce the frequency of exacerbations and improve the quality of life of patients.*

Keywords: *small airways, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.*

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is an irreversible but treatable disease characterized primarily by shortness of breath, cough and sputum production [1]. According to results of the Global Burden of Disease (GBD), it generated that global age-standardized COPD prevalence vary between 2% to 5% across years, representing variable estimates of 328 million people with COPD in 2010, 299 million in 2017 and 212 million in 2019[3]. COPD is characterized by systemic involvement and multiple comorbidities. Their frequency increases with age, which leads to a decrease in the quality of life of patients with COPD and complicates its treatment. Small airway disease (SAD) is a key feature of COPD, and has been studied extensively over many decades.

Small airway dysfunction plays a significant role in the pathogenesis of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). These pathways can become a site of significant resistance to airflow due to their narrowness, inflammation, hyperresponsiveness, and structural changes such as fibrosis or loss of elasticity [1,2]. Obstruction of the small airways leads to decreased alveolar ventilation, which reduces gas exchange and causes chronic hypoxemia. This affects overall respiratory resistance and increases disease progression, increasing the risk of exacerbations and mortality [4,5].

The structure of the small airways (SAT) plays an important role in the functioning of the respiratory system. This is especially noticeable in diseases such as bronchial asthma and COPD. Normally, the small bronchi are involved in the conduction of air and the exchange of gases, but in various diseases they can be affected, which leads to deterioration of lung function. In recent years, studies of small airway epithelial cells have shown their significant role in innate immunity and as potential targets for new drugs. Epithelial cells act as the body's first line of defense, preventing germs and viruses from penetrating mucous membranes. They are actively involved in detecting pathogens and triggering an immune response through receptors and signaling proteins. These cells are capable of producing various immune mediators and cytokines, which makes them active participants in immune reactions [6,7,8].

Mucin plays a central role in the functioning of the small respiratory system, especially in the context of chronic respiratory diseases such as COPD (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease). It is responsible for creating a mucosal barrier that protects epithelial cells from external influences and promotes hydration and protection of the respiratory tract [9].

Mucin regulates mucus secretion by participating in mucociliary clearance and air purification from pathogens and pollutants [10]. Mucin also helps maintain proper moisture in the airways, which is critical to prevent tissue drying and damage.

Cilia in the small airways perform critical functions in maintaining normal functioning of the respiratory system [11,12]. They not only promote mucociliary clearance by transporting mucus, pollutants and pathogens out of the lungs, but also play a role in the sensory and protective functions of the lungs [13,14].

Research shows that motile cilia, formed during the differentiation of epithelial cells, contribute to effective airway clearance [15], which is critical for preventing infections and maintaining homeostasis in the lungs. However, in chronic diseases such as COPD, ciliary function may be impaired due to structural changes in the airways, including epithelial changes and increased mucus, which aggravate disease symptoms [16,17]. In COPD, small airway disease is characterized by airway remodeling, mucus obstruction, and immune cell infiltration [18, 19]. Damage caused by factors such as smoking or infection triggers the wound healing process, which leads to an increase in the thickness of the airway wall and, accordingly, to a decrease in their lumen [20,21]. Immune cell infiltration involves the recruitment of increased numbers of macrophages, neutrophils, CD20+ B cells and CD4+ and CD8+ T cells, with CD8+ T cells suggested to play a leading role in small airway obstruction and tissue injury [22,26]. Lung hyperinflation is a common cause of shortness of breath and functional limitations in patients with COPD. Small airway disease can lead to expiratory flow limitation, pulmonary gas retention, and dynamic hyperinflation [23]. This is characterized by straightening of the diaphragm, protrusion of the sternum, kyphosis of the chest and widening of the intercostal spaces, which leads to the formation of a barrel-shaped chest. Dynamic hyperinflation develops as a result of restriction of expiratory airflow combined with a decrease in expiratory time, such as during exercise, and is associated with a decrease in inspirational capacity and an increase in functional residual capacity. Small airway disease and emphysema are associated with decreased FEV1, especially in mild to moderate COPD. Treatment targeting the small airways in COPD may reduce the rate of progression of emphysema [24,25]. In fact, because small airway disease appears to precede the onset of emphysema, the development of treatments specifically targeting small airway disease has the potential to treat the progression of both bronchial and parenchymal diseases [26].

Thus, the study of the small airways is important for understanding and treating various respiratory diseases, especially chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). These pathways are a key site where important pathological processes occur, including inflammation, remodeling and mucus accumulation, leading to airway obstruction and decreased lung function.

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